

ENVIRONMENTAL POLLUTION AND SUSTAINABLE WASTE MANAGEMENT PROCESS IN AKWA IBOM STATE: IMPLICATIONS ON PUBLIC HEALTH AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The research was set to provide ways of reducing the impact of environmental pollution on public health and socio-economic development through sustainable waste management process in Akwa Ibom State. The study adopted historical and descriptive methods of enquiry and gathered relevant data from secondary sources. although with some scientific observations across the 56 waste dumpsites (as spotted in the map in p. 22 below) in Uyo municipality. The research made use of the theories of modernization (with its different variances or schools of thought), by John Maynard Keynes, particularly, the Social-Cultural Theory, by Hoselitz, Talcott Parson and Manning Nash, etc. According to the author, theorists that share this theoretical perspective believe that it is the changes in the social, cultural and institutional systems that create the necessary condition which usher in economic development. Hoselitz for instance, argues that we must concern ourselves with the question of the change that occurs in a social milieu as it leaves or before it leaves its precious state of relatively slow growth or even stagnation and starts a process of rapid economic growth. Four findings were made, among others was that apart from the monthly sanitation usually conducted by the state government on the last Saturday of every month in the state, Local Government Areas do not, on their own embark on sanitation exercises. Based on those findings, it was recommended among others that, the Commissioner for Environment and Mineral Resources, should get all the 31 Local Government Areas actively involved in the ministry's partnerships with private sector to aid government agencies toward maintaining a clean and green environment all over the state. As a follow-up, the commissioner should make efforts to keep records of environmental situation at the local government levels through their monthly performance reports.

Keywords: Pollution, Waste Management, Public Health, Socio-Economic Development.

1 Introduction

1.1 Background to the Study

Environmental pollution and sustainable waste management process in Akwa Ibom State: implications for public health and socio-economic development, if viewed from the "public utility" perspective or what is referred by some ancient scholars as "public good" we would then meet such renowned philosophers as Plato in his Plato Republic (1941), Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832), John Stuart Mill (1806-1873), Thomas Hobbes (1588-1679) and John Rawls (1971). Other very prominent writers associated with public interest and/or public goods include: Machiavelli, Hegel, Edmond Burke and Karl Marx (1818-1883). It may be interesting to note that even from more recent records are such philosophers as Herbart A. Simon, Charles. E. Lindblum, Amitai Etzioni, A. Waldafky, and of course, V. C. Uchendu who have also contemporaneously contributed to the public interest debate in recent times.

Plato uses the term, "common good" to refer to "public interest" truths or principles or thoughts for the formulation of any public policy in order to ensure that provision, by the state of the greatest happiness for the greatest number of persons is largely upheld in any society.

Ekpe () in Okereke (2003) made an impressive reference to both Bentham and Mill on the concept of utilitarianism, which still boils down to this issue of public good or public interest. According to Ekpe,

Utilitarianism as espoused by its major exponents, Jeremy Bentham (1748-1832) and John Stuart Mill (1806-1873) advocated for the provision, by the state, of the greatest happiness for the greatest number of persons". This position, according to Ekpe (), "has been re-echoed and amplified in the last two centuries by political economists, particularly those of the Marxist persuasion. Their postulations and expositions have exerted profound impact on the public policy of many countries. It has also transformed the contour of capitalism." He further stressed that, "the fast decomposition or orthodox capitalism, and the ever-increasing intervention of the state in economic domain is indicative of the influence of utilitarianism. Today, an integral part of the economic agenda of the state is to provide what Laski calls 'special good on the largest scale'. However, the thesis of modernization school just as entrenched in the theoretical framework and as premised on the fact that underdevelopment in the Third World is internally generated and perpetuated due to the traditional and primitive character of these societies may gain more strength by Professor Ogbuagu's opinion in Bassey (2015) that "most developing nations still face serious and worsening economic conditions arising

either from internal socio-political and economic problems or as a result of the often criticized asymmetrical relations between the North and the South.

In view of the foregoing, Nigeria has over the years tried to raise its socio-economic status by way of improving on its infrastructures, providing good health-care services and free education, ensuring maintenance culture and supporting clean and healthy environment, etc. Furthermore, Akwa Ibom State, through the Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources has, apart from her monthly sanitation exercises on the last Saturdays of every month in the state adopted this policy of healthy environment. It has frequently and proactively intervened in the routine evacuation of refuse as well as carrying out waste management practices in the state with a view to presenting a clean and green environment for a safer public health of the citizens towards a smooth socio-economic development in the state.

This study attempts to examine the extent of government's involvement in the

waste management process in the state; whether indeed, the management process is sustainable in nature as encapsulated in the topic; what the state government is doing to curb or reduce pollution menace, be it environmental pollution, air pollution, water pollution, or land pollution, etc. with a view to preserving the general public health of its citizenry and encouraging socio-economic development in the state. Other areas of concentration will include: conceptual explication in which pollution, waste, management, waste management, socio-economic development and public health are defined; government policy, implementation strategies, theoretical framework and the specific cases as Itam and Akpan Andem markets in Uyo municipality will be considered among other important topics before conclusion. Finally, all the sources of our information systematically chronicled in the reference section of the study.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The adage that, "Cleanliness is next to godliness" has in recent times been grossly undermined and filthiness of the human environment through indiscriminate dumping of refuse has become the order of the day, just as there is also high rise in percentage or magnitude of environmental pollution of all sorts in the society.

On the one hand, environmental pollution ranging from smokes emanating from burning; smells from heaps of dumpsites; greenhouse gas emission; automobile combustion; and, industrial activities like gas flaring and oil spills; all have various effects on human health through the intake of food, water and air. Bush or other forms of burning; smells, odours or stench from dumpsites; greenhouse gas emission; automobile combustion and gas flaring, all impact the air space, directly, as well as human health, indirectly, through breathing. Whereas, oil spills affect the water

habitats and roof tops directly, thereby rendering water that comes from those sources harmful, unhealthy and undrinkable. The terrestrial lives existing in the waters are at risk. Whoever eats fishes affected by oil spills in the water or drink such water, stands the risk of being infected or dead.

On the other hand, excessive and indiscriminate wastes disposal on the streets can easily cause cholera or dysentery due to the stench it produces over time. During heavy rainy season the heaps of refuse are eroded into the quarters thereby causing blockades on the drainage and making it difficult for water to flow. This situation usually breeds mosquitoes and other organisms that can affect human health. All these developments, especially the emission and flaring of gases and smokes have eventually affected the ozone layer thereby, causing its depletion. The depletion of the ozone layer further brings about climate change which poses serious challenges on human health.

Based on the foregoing, this research is mainly set to investigate the implications of environmental pollution and waste management process on public health and socio-economic development in Akwa Ibom State. In order to achieve this main objective, some questions will need to be answered that bothers on the role of the 31 Local Government Areas of Akwa Ibom State in the waste management process; understanding the involvement of individual families and homes and the possible methods that they adopt in the wastes management process; probing to know whether or not there is a mechanism for a regular evacuation of wastes management in the state; establishing whether there is provision for the day-to-day cleaning and sweeping of streets and major roads and regular silting of quarters in the cities, etc.

1.3 Objectives of the Study

The main objective of the study is to investigate the implications of environmental pollution and waste management process on public health and socio-economic development in Akwa Ibom State.

Whereas, the subsidiary objectives include:

- i. To find out whether the 31 Local Government Areas, on their own use to embark on sanitation exercises apart from the monthly sanitation usually conducted by the state government on the last Saturday of every month in the state.
- ii. To verify the methods of wastes disposal that individual families and homes in Uyo municipality adopt in the process of managing their domestic wastes in the state.
- iii. To confirm whether there is a mechanism for a regular evacuation of wastes from the various dumpsites in different streets to the central dumpsite Akwa

Ibom State.

- iv. To find out if the state government has also made provision for the day-to-day cleaning and sweeping of streets and major roads and regular silting of quarters in the cities, apart from evacuating wastes and checking environmental pollution.

1.4 Research Questions

The study posed four questions for the purpose of eliciting answers from respondents on the subject matter.

- i. Do the 31 Local Government Areas, on their own embark on sanitation exercises apart from the monthly sanitation usually conducted by the state government on the last Saturday of every month in the state?
- ii. What are the methods of wastes disposal that individual families and homes in Uyo municipality adopt in the process of managing their domestic wastes in the state?
- iii. Is there a mechanism for a regular evacuation of wastes from the various dumpsites in different streets to the central dumpsite Akwa Ibom State?
- iv. Has the state government also made provision for the day-to-day cleaning and sweeping of streets and major roads and regular silting of quarters in the cities, apart from evacuating wastes and checking environmental pollution?

1.5 Research Hypotheses

The four null (Ho) research hypotheses bellow were postulated from the research questions, in order to be able to carry out empirical tests on respondents.

- i. The 31 Local Government Areas, on their own do not use to embark on sanitation exercises apart from the monthly sanitation usually conducted by the state government on the last Saturday of every month in the state.
- ii. There are no definite methods of wastes disposal that individual families and homes in Uyo municipality adopt in the process of managing their domestic wastes in the state.
- iii. There is no established mechanism for a regular evacuation of wastes from the various dumpsites in different streets to the central dumpsite Akwa Ibom State.
- iv. The state government has not also made provision for the day-to-day cleaning and sweeping of streets and major roads and regular silting of quarters in the cities, apart from evacuating wastes and checking environmental pollution.

1.6 Conceptual Explications

Pollution: The term, "pollution" in Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary of current English (Ninth Edition) is defined as, "the process of making air, water, soil. etc., dirty; the state of being dirty".

Environment: The natural world in which people, animals and plants live is what is

called the environment. Environmental: Connected with the natural conditions in which people, animals and plants live; connected with the environment.

Environmental Pollution: Environmental pollution is basically the "process of making the environment dirty or the state of the environment being dirty".

Waste: It is observed that the term, "waste" has so many meanings and connotations depending on its usage. In this context, we are considering "waste" as "materials that are no longer needed and are thrown away: e.g. household/industrial waste. As a follow up to this definition, waste disposal which in the course of our study will gain a prominent section in our discourse can be defined as the "process of getting rid of waste".

Management: This term is defined in the Oxford Learner's Dictionary of current English as, "the act of running and controlling a business or similar organisation". Management is regarded as the collective utilization of human and material resources in an effort to reach the defined goals of the organisation (Naidus, 2011). In elucidating further definition of management, Nwachukw (2006) in Udoh (2014) has stated that "different meanings have been attributed to the word, "management".

According to him, "some people see it as referring to a group of people. They think of management team or of individuals in an organization. Management is also seen as a process demanding the performance of a specific American Institute of Management holds that, to a student, management is an academic discipline. In this instance, people study the art of managing or management science. The author further added that management can be defined as "getting things done through and with others". This can be more scientifically defined as, "the coordination of all the resources of an organization through the process of planning, organizing, directing and controlling in order to attain organizational objective. Management is the guidance or direction of people towards organizational goals or objectives. It can also be seen as the supervising, controlling and coordinating of activities to attain optimum results with organizational resource".

Waste Management: If "waste" are materials that are no longer needed and are thrown away", while "management" is seen as, "the supervising, controlling and coordinating of activities to attain optimum result with organizational resource", then, what is waste management? In putting the two words together, waste management could be the process in which materials are supervised, controlled and coordinated to attain optimum result, which is the cleanliness of the society within the limit of organizational resource. In the context of this chapter, we recall that the Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources acts as the organizational agency that represents the government of Akwa Ibom State in the maintenance of cleaning

the state. The Ministry, apart from engaging every citizen and resident of the state on the last Saturday of every month on what it calls, "State Environmental Sanitation Exercise", for the general cleaning up of the state, it also ensures the setting up of "Green Brigade" and agency of the Ministry that engages people on temporary basis to clean up the metropolis through cutting of grasses; sweeping of roads, markets and parks; and, moving of garbage to the dumping site. A step further in this process of supervising, controlling and coordinating of activities of waste management in the state by the Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources is in providing waste bins across major streets and roads in the state capital for the purposes of gathering waste from the domestic environment and avoiding incessant littering of the environment with waste materials. It would interest you to know that the Ministry engages permanent staff and purchases sewage trucks that go round the city on a daily basis to evacuate the waste bins to their sewage dump site.

In this study, the problem is not really hinged on the method or the process of the metropolitan management of waste materials, because admittedly, the process is excellently followed in Uyo, the Akwa Ibom State capital for over about a decade now. But, the intention is to investigate the pollution that is generated at the waste dumpsites, how it is managed by the state; how it affects the health status of the citizens of the state. And, if it does, how it has further affected or otherwise, the socio-economic development of the state. It is important, therefore, to state here that waste management systems can be seen in three dimensions, namely: domestic, industrial and public waste management systems.

Public Health: The term, "public" refers to what belongs to everybody as provided by government. Therefore, "public" in this sense, could be defined as government's provision, "for the use of people in general". Whereas, "health" means, "the condition of a person's body or mind". The Oxford Advance learner's Dictionary of current English goes ahead to give a beautiful example, thus: "Exhaust fumes are bad for your health". This is typical of air pollution which will also form the bulk of our concentration. But what is public health? Public health can be said to be the condition of a person's body or mind as cared for or enhanced by healthy environment, surroundings, health care provisions as well as health conditions of service by government to the public or the generality of the people in society. It is this public health condition that we will seek to know whether the management of waste material has either increased or reduced the level of environmental pollution in the state and to what extent has that affected the socio-economic development of the state.

Economic Development: More often than not, the term 'development' is used in an exclusive economic sense - the justification being that the type of economy is itself an index of other social features. What then is economic development? A society

develops economically as its members jointly increase their capacity for dealing with the environment. This capacity for dealing with the environment is dependent on the extent to which they understand the laws of nature (science), on the extent to which they put that understanding into practice by devising tools (technology), and on the manner in which work is organized.

Taking a long term view, it can be said that there has been constant economic development within human society since the origin of man, because man has multiplied enormously his capacity to win a living from nature. The magnitude of man's achievement is best understood by reflecting on the early history of human society and noting the following: firstly, the progress from the crude stone tools to the use of metals; secondly, the change over from hunting and gathering wild fruit to the domestication of animals and the growing of food crops; and thirdly, the improvement in organization of work from being an individualistic activity towards being an activity which assumes a social character through the participation of many.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Public health Rhodes and Bryant (2018) have defined public health as "the art and science of preventing disease, prolonging life, and promoting physical and mental health, sanitation, personal hygiene, control of infectious diseases, and organization of health services". From the normal human interactions involved in dealing with the many problems of social life, there has emerged recognition of the importance of community action in the promotion of health and the prevention and treatment of disease, and this is expressed in the concept of public health.

Comparable terms for public health medicine are social medicine and community medicine; the latter has been widely adopted in the United Kingdom, and the practitioners are called community physicians. The practice of public health draws heavily on medical science and philosophy and concentrates especially on manipulating and controlling the environment for the benefit of the public. It is concerned therefore with housing, water supplies, and food. Noxious agents can be introduced into these through farming, fertilizers, inadequate sewage disposal and drainage, construction, defective heating and ventilating systems, machinery, and toxic chemicals. Public health medicine is part of the greater enterprise of preserving and improving the public health. Community physicians cooperate with diverse groups, from architects, builders, sanitary and heating and ventilating engineers, and factory and food inspectors to psychologists and sociologists, chemists, physicists, and toxicologists. Occupational medicine is concerned with the health, safety, and welfare of persons in the workplace. It may be viewed as a specialized part of public health medicine since its aim is to reduce the risks in the environment in which persons work

The venture of preserving, maintaining, and actively promoting public health requires special methods of information-gathering (epidemiology) and corporate arrangements to act upon significant findings and put them into practice. Statistics collected by epidemiologists attempt to describe and explain the occurrence of disease in a population by correlating factors such as diet, environment, radiation exposure, or cigarette smoking with the incidence and prevalence of disease. The government, through laws and regulations, creates agencies to oversee and formally inspect and monitor water supplies, food processing, sewage treatment, drains, and pollution. Governments also are concerned with the control of epidemic diseases. establishing guidelines for appropriate medical responses and isolation procedures. and issuing travel warnings to prevent the spread of disease from affected areas.

Various public health agencies have been established to help control and monitor disease within societies, on both national and international levels. For example, the United Kingdom's Public Health Act of 1848 established a special public health ministry for England and Wales. In the United States, public health is studied and coordinated on a national level by the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention (CDC). Internationally, the World Health Organization (WHO) plays an equivalent role. WHO is especially important in providing assistance for the implementation of organizational and administrative methods of handling problems associated with health and disease in less-developed countries worldwide. Within these countries, health problems, limitations of resources, education of health personnel, and other factors must be taken into account in designing health service systems.

Advances in science and medicine in developed countries, including the generation of vaccines and antibiotics, have been fundamental in bringing vital aid to countries afflicted by a high burden of disease. Yet, despite the expansion of resources and improvements in the mobilization of these resources to the most severely afflicted areas, the incidence of preventable disease and of neglected tropical disease remains exceptionally high worldwide. Reducing the impact and prevalence of these diseases is a major goal of international public health. The persistence of such diseases in the world, however, serves as an important indication of the difficulties that health organizations and societies continue to confront.

Pollution

Pollution is a term which is heard every other day at school, college and read about it in newspapers. So what is it? Pollution occurs when pollutants contaminate the natural surroundings; which brings about changes that affect our normal lifestyles adversely. Pollutants are the key elements or components of pollution which are generally waste materials of different forms. Pollution disturbs our ecosystem and the balance in the environment. With modernization and development in our lives pollution has reached its peak, giving rise to global warming and human illness.

Pollution occurs in different forms; air, water, soil, radioactive, noise mermal and light. Every form of pollution has two sources of occurrence; the point and the non-point sources. The point sources are easy to identify, monitor and control, whereas the non-point sources are hard to control. Let us discuss the different types of pollutions, their causes and effects on mankind and the environment as a whole.

Types and Causes of Pollution

Air Pollution is the most prominent and dangerous form of pollution. It occurs due to many reasons. Excessive burning of fuel which is a necessity of our daily lives for cooking, driving and other industrial activities; releases a huge amount of chemical substances in the air every day; these pollute the air. Smoke from chimneys, factories, vehicles or burning of wood basically occurs due to coal burning; this releases Sulphur dioxide into the air making it toxic. The effects of air pollution are evident too. Release of Sulphur dioxide and hazardous gases into the air causes global warming and acid rain; which in turn have increased temperatures, erratic rains and droughts worldwide; making it tough for the animals to survive. We breathe in every polluted particle from the air; result is increase in asthma and cancer in the lungs.

Water Pollution has taken toll of all the surviving species of the earth. Almost 60% of the species live in water bodies. It occurs due to several factors; the industrial wastes dumped into the rivers and other water bodies cause an imbalance in the water leading to its severe contamination and death of aquatic species. If you suspect that nearby water sources have been contaminated by a corporation then it might be a good idea to hire an expert to see your options.

Also spraying insecticides, pesticides like DDT on plants pollutes the ground water system and oil spills in the oceans have caused irreparable damage to the water bodies. Eutrophication is another big source; it occurs due to daily activities like washing clothes, utensils near lakes, ponds or rivers; this forces detergents to go into water which blocks sunlight from penetrating, thus reducing oxygen and making it inhabitable.

Water pollution not only harms the aquatic beings but it also contaminates the entire food chain by severely affecting human dependent on these. Water-borne diseases like cholera, diarrhea has also increased in all places.

Soil pollution occurs due to incorporation of unwanted chemicals in the soil due to human activities. Use of insecticides and pesticides absorbs the nitrogen compounds from the soil making it unfit for plants to derive nutrition from. Release of industrial waste, mining and deforestation also exploits the soil. Since plants can't grow properly, they can't hold the soil and this leads to soil erosion.

Noise pollution is caused when noise which is an unpleasant sound affects our ears and leads to psychological problems like stress, hypertension, hearing impairment, etc. It is caused by machines in industries, loud music, etc.

Radioactive pollution is highly dangerous when it occurs. It can occur due to nuclear plant malfunctions, improper nuclear waste disposal, accidents, etc. It causes cancer, infertility, blindness, and defects at the time of birth; can sterilize soil and affect air and water.

Thermal/heat pollution is due to the excess heat in the environment creating unwanted changes over long time periods; due to huge number of industrial plants, deforestation and air pollution. It increases the earth's temperature, causing drastic climatic changes and extinction of wildlife.

Light pollution occurs due to prominent excess illumination of an area. It is largely visible in big cities, on advertising boards and billboards, in sports or entertainment events at the night. In residential areas, the lives of the inhabitants are greatly affected by this. It also affects the astronomical observations and activities by making the stars almost invisible.

Effects of Pollution

1. **Environment Degradation:** Environment is the first casualty for increase in pollution weather in air or water. The increase in the amount of CO₂ in the atmosphere leads to smog which can restrict sunlight from reaching the earth thus, preventing plants in the process of photosynthesis. Gases like Sulfur dioxide and nitrogen oxide can cause acid rain. Water pollution in terms of Oil spill may lead to death of several wildlife species.

2. **Human Health:** The decrease in quality of air leads to several respiratory problems including asthma or lung cancer. Chest pain, congestion, throat inflammation, cardiovascular disease, respiratory diseases are some of the diseases that can be caused by air pollution. Water pollution occurs due to contamination of water and may pose skin related problems including skin irritations and rashes. Similarly, Noise pollution leads to hearing loss, stress and sleep disturbance.

3. **Global Warming:** The emission of greenhouse gases particularly CO₂, is leading to global warming. Every other day new industries are being set up, new vehicles come on roads and trees are cut to make way for new homes. All of them, in direct or indirect way lead to increase in CO₂ in the environment. The increase in CO₂ leads to melting of polar ice caps which increases the sea level and pose danger for the people living near coastal areas.

4. **Ozone Layer Depletion:** Ozone layer is the thin shield high up in the sky that stops ultra violet rays from reaching the earth. As a result of human activities, chemicals, such as chlorofluorocarbons (CFCs), were released into the atmosphere which contributed to the depletion of ozone layer.

5. **Infertile Land:** Due to constant use of insecticides and pesticides, the soil may become infertile. Plants may not be able to grow properly. Various forms of chemicals produced from industrial waste is released into the flowing water which also affects the quality of soil.

Pollution not only affect humans by destroying their respiratory, cardiovascular and neurological systems; it also affects the nature, plants, fruits, vegetables, rivers, ponds, forests, animals, etc., on which they are highly dependent for survival. It is crucial to control pollution as the nature, wildlife and human life are precious gifts to the mankind.

Waste Management

Americans alone are responsible for producing a whopping 220 million tons of waste a year. This number is far more than any other nation in the world. Because of this fact both the government and environmental associations have developed numerous methods of dealing with the problem. Waste management is that solution, a rather complex issue that encompasses more than 20 different industries. Waste management is collection, transportation, and disposal of garbage, sewage and other waste products. Waste management is the process of treating solid wastes and offers variety of solutions for recycling items that don't belong to trash. It is about how garbage can be used as a valuable resource. Waste management is something that each and every household and business owner in the world needs. Waste management disposes of the products and substances that you have use in a safe and efficient manner.

"Waste management or Waste disposal is all the activities and actions required to manage waste from its inception to its final disposal. This includes amongst other things, collection, transport, treatment and disposal of waste together with monitoring and regulation. It also encompasses the legal and regulatory framework that relates to waste management encompassing guidance on recycling etc." (Wikipedia, 2018).

It would be recalled that there are eight major groups of waste management methods, each of them divided into numerous categories. Those groups include source reduction and reuse, animal feeding, recycling, composting, fermentation, landfills, incineration and land application. You can start using many techniques right at home,

like reduction and reuse, which works to reduce the amount of disposable material used.

Various Methods of Waste Disposal

There are many methods available to dispose waste. Let's take a look at some of the most commonly used methods that we should know about waste management.

Landfills: Throwing daily waste/garbage in the landfills is the most popularly used method of waste disposal used today. This process of waste disposal focuses attention on burying the waste in the land. Landfills are commonly found in developing countries. There is a process used that eliminates the odors and dangers of waste before it is placed into the ground. While it is true this is the most popular form of waste disposal, it is certainly far from the only procedure and one that may also bring with it an assortment of space. This method is becoming less these days although, thanks to the lack of space available and the strong presence of methane and other landfill gases, both of which can cause numerous contamination problems. Landfills give rise to air and water pollution which severely affects the environment and can prove fatal to the lives of humans and animals. Many areas are reconsidering the use of landfills.

Incineration/Combustion: Incineration or combustion is a type of disposal method in which municipal solid wastes are burned at high temperatures so as to convert them into residue and gaseous products. The biggest advantage of this type of method is that it can reduce the volume of solid waste to 20 to 30 percent of the original volume, decreases the space they take up and reduce the stress on landfills. This process is also known as thermal treatment where solid waste materials are converted by Incinerators into heat, gas, steam and ash. Incineration is something that is very useful in countries where landfill space is no longer available, which includes Japan.

Recovery and Recycling: Resource recovery is the process of taking useful discarded items for a specific next use. These discarded items are then processed to extract or recover materials and resources or convert them to energy in the form of useable heat, electricity or fuel. Recycling is the process of converting waste products into new products to prevent energy usage and consumption of fresh raw materials. Recycling is the third component of Reduce, Reuse and Recycle waste hierarchy. The idea behind recycling is to reduce energy usage, reduce volume of landfills, reduce air and water pollution, reduce greenhouse gas emissions and preserve natural resources for future use.

Plasma Gasification: Plasma gasification is another form of waste management. Plasma is a primarily an electrically charged or a highly ionized gas. Lighting is one

type of plasma which produces temperatures that exceed waste disposal, a vessel uses characteristic plasma torches operating at +10,000 °F which is creating a gasification zone till 3,000 °F for the conversion of solid or liquid wastes into a syngas. During the treatment solid waste by plasma gasification, the waste's molecular bonds are broken down as result of the intense heat in the vessels and the elemental components. Thanks to this process, destruction of waste and dangerous materials is found. This form of waste disposal provides renewable energy and an assortment of other fantastic benefits.

Composting: Composting is an easy and natural bio-degradation process that takes organic wastes i.e. remains of plants and garden and kitchen waste and turns into nutrient rich food for your plants. Composting, normally used for organic farming, occurs by allowing organic materials to sit in one place for months until microbes decompose it. Composting is one of the best methods of waste disposal as it can turn unsafe organic products into safe compost. On the other side, it is slow process and takes lot of space.

Waste to Energy (Recover Energy): Waste to energy (WtE) process involves converting of non-recyclable waste items into useable heat, electricity, or fuel through a variety of processes. This type of source of energy is a renewable energy source as non-recyclable waste can be used over and over again to create energy. It can also help to reduce carbon emissions by offsetting the need for energy from fossil sources. Waste-to-Energy, also widely recognized by its acronym WtE is the generation of energy in the form of heat or electricity from waste.

Avoidance/Waste Minimization: The easiest method of waste management is to reduce creation of waste materials thereby reducing the amount of waste going to landfills. Waste reduction can be done through recycling old materials like jar, bags, repairing broken items instead of buying new one, avoiding use of disposable products like plastic bags, reusing second hand items, and buying items that uses less designing. Recycling and composting is a couple of the best methods of waste management. Composting is so far only possible on a small scale, either by private individuals or in areas where waste can be mixed with farming soil or used for landscaping purposes. Recycling is widely used around the world, with plastic, paper and metal leading the list of the most recyclable items. Most material recycled is reused for its original purpose.

The Bottom Line: There are certain waste types that are considered as hazardous and cannot be disposed of without special handling which will prevent contamination from occurring. Biomedical waste is one example of such. This is found in health care facilities and similar institutions. As we can see there are plenty

of important things that we should know about waste management and disposal in order to ensure that we are safe, as well as that we are keeping the environment safe. It is our choices as to how we will dispose of waste, however it is always in our best interest to take a look at all of the options that we have available before making the choices.

Locations of waste receptacles and the sample sites on the map of Uyo Municipality

Source: field Survey, 2022

Waste Dump and Collection Method in Uyo Municipality

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Government and Citizens' Involvement in Waste Management in Akwa Ibom State

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Source: Field Survey, 2022

Theoretical Framework

In thinking about what theory could best suit this topic, The Theories of Modernization readily came to mind. But, it should be noted that modernization theories have different variance or schools of thought, namely: The Economic Theory by Thirlwall and John Maynard Keynes; The Psychological/Idiosyncratic Theory like the theory of authoritarian traditional societies by Everette E. Hagen; The Institutional Theory by C. E. Black, Professor Samuel P. Huntington, Lacion W. Pye, etc. although Pye has been strongly criticized by Professor Claude Ake on Pye's political development/institutional theorizing. The final stream of the theories of modernization is The Social-Cultural Theory, by Hoselitz, Talcott Parson and Manning Nash, etc.

Although the social-cultural theory had been criticized by Smock and Smock as well as Professor Francis Idachaba, this theory presents the most suitable framework for this study. As such, we adopt the social-cultural theory of the modernization school to discuss our topic: Environmental pollution and sustainable waste management process in Akwa Ibom State: implications for public health and socio-economic development.

The Social-Cultural Theory

Okereke (2010) has considered the social-cultural theory in an elaborate manner which to me, can help in putting this work in its right perspective and in focus if followed concisely. According to the author, theorists that share this theoretical perspective believe that it is the changes in the social, cultural and institutional systems that create the necessary condition which usher in economic development.

Hoselitz () for instance, argues that we must concern ourselves with the question of the change that occurs in a social milieu as it leaves or before it leaves its precious state of relatively slow growth or even stagnation and starts a process of rapid economic growth. He maintains that it is necessary to identify those cultural conditions, which enhance the capacity of an economy to save and invest a larger proportion of its net income than was hitherto possible.

Hoselitz () drew widely from Talcott Parson's Pattern Variables to illustrate the above position. These variables are dichotomized cultural and social behaviours, representing polar extremes of either universalism or particularism, achievement or ascription, specificity or diffuseness, affectivity or affective neutrality, and self-oriented or collective orientation. The implication of this argument is that the developed countries are developed because they exhibit cultural traits characterized by universalism, achievement, specificity, affective-neutrality and self-orientation, while the developing countries exhibit their opposites, that is, particularism, ascription, diffuseness, affectivity and collective-orientation.

This view has, however, been criticized. For instance, Offong () argues that empirical evidence in both developed and under-developed countries does not support "the

presumed meritocracy and particularistic criteria. This derives from the observation that Japanese industrialization "is believed to have been aided by particularistic principles", factories in Japan have had to employ a whole family based on kinship ties making the factories look like units of families. Furthermore, Offong (), argues that even though the United States and Europe are industrialized, one still observes relationships largely based on particularistic considerations.

In point of fact, Okereke (2010) goes further that, Manning Nash, one of the socio-cultural theorists, recognizes the existence of diverse cultures, noting that people of different cultures respond differently to change and may not adopt the same strategies of development. It is also the contention of Nash that since economic development is a process of social change, it must be seen to involve three related kinds of social action, namely:

- i. The choice to institute changes;
- ii. The bringing together of the means and facilities to implement the choice, and
- iii. The organization of social and cultural life so that growth becomes a built-in feature of the social system.

Nash (), according to Okereke (2010), further identifies lack of capital for productive investment as one of the many problems facing third world countries. He adds however, that his study of Burma and Cambodia has shown that the social structures and cultural patterns which enhance saving and investments vary from country to country. Professor Francis Idachaba, on his own part, contends that if developing countries are really interested in planned change in the peasant economy, such change requires identification of these positive elements within the cultures of developing societies that promote change while at the same time identifying those that can possibly constitute obstacles to change. He thus emphasized the need to create an environment which will make it possible for planned change to be adopted to the cultural and social values of those who are supposed to adopt the change (Okereke, 2010).

Socio-Economic Challenges in Uyo Metropolis viz: Urua Akpan Andem and Urua Itam

There are myriads of socio-economic challenges arising from environmental pollution ranging from domestic level to institutional, up to industrial level. Most of the environmental pollutions have direct effect on the air and air pollution affects lives and properties adversely thereby rendering socio-economic development of a place stagnant.

The problems posed by the sewage dumping sites by Wellington Basseway Way, behind the Governor's Office Annex, Uyo are quite numerous. Some of these problems

include adverse air pollution through stinking smell and gaseous emission, littering of surrounding environment to domination and destruction of large span of farm land where the waste and sewage are dumped.

The adverse effect of this situation on the socio-economic development of the state, instead of value chain, has denied land owners of the ownership of those portions of dump sites. This situation has hindered farming activities that should occur on those sites thereby leading to production of large/commercial farm products. The gaseous emission has affected lives and property of citizens, particularly those living around the dump sites. Some lives have been lost as a result of this emission. The roofs of houses built around these dump sites are not only destroyed by gases flared from these sites, the water dropping from the roofs during rainy seasons are badly contaminated and it destroys both human and animals when used.

By implication, when human lives as well as animals are at jeopardy as a result of the activities of these dump sites, there is a direct effect on the progress of socio-economic development in the society. On the property, houses built around these dump sites will not be attractive for renting by tenants. That alone renders the landlords' income levels redundant. Furthermore, the landlords may not be motivated or excited to push toward requesting for Certificate of Occupancy (C of O) from the state government. What that means is that the landlord will not be opportune to seek facilities from the Banks for higher economic application of his resources. And, of course, even if the landlords were to have the C of Os for their houses situated around the dump sites, the Banks on their parts, may not find it as good business to use such houses as collaterals for facilities to those landlords due to bad locations of the houses, should there be incidence of default of repayment of facility by the landlords.

At Urua Akpan Andem and Urua Itam, although the State Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources is doing commendable work in the evacuation of refuse waste from time to time, but their exercises are basically on the main roads and major streets of Uyo. The situation is still bad within the markets, especially during market days when business is going on.

There are still stumps of refuse here and there inside the markets. Gutters are over-flown with dirt and blackishly dirty water with stinking smell. These stagnant waters in turn breed mosquitoes which lead to infestation of malaria parasites on the traders, thereby slowing down the socio-economic activities in the markets. This situation namely, the effect on public health in turn does affect the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) of the state.

Rapid rise in rural to urban migration has worsened environmental conditions for cities and towns in Akwa Ibom State, leaving local authorities to battle unsuccessfully with mounting waste generated daily by residents.

Accordingly, the streets of major towns like Abak, Ikot Abasi, Ikot Ekpene, Oron, Eket, Uyo are littered with heaps of smelly, decomposing, vermin infested, disease causing filth while public and private waste management agencies struggle with ramshackle tools and machines to remedy the situation.

Reports reveal that about 30,350 metric tons of Municipal Solid Waste, (MSW), is generated daily in Uyo urban centre alone. Much of this trash is created by over 350, 000 households living in the metropolis including major markets such as Urua Akpan Andem, Urua Itam and ubiquitous street markets.

The Akwa Ibom State Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources is responsible for Waste Management and Pollution Control across the state, but apparently its area of influence does not exceed Uyo capital city development area.

Unfortunately, while the state environment ministry has recorded several successful initiatives in keeping the metropolis clean, neighbouring towns remain an eyesore. For instance, the ministry recently entered a partnership with Zenith Bank Plc towards promoting a cleaner and healthier environment in the state.

Furthermore, the green army initiative, which was introduced during the last administration, is still doing a remarkable job, keeping the streets of Uyo neat. The same, however, cannot be said of similar initiatives introduced by some local government authorities. Street sweepers and sanitation workers are bedeviled with unpaid stipends, low morale and dilapidated infrastructure.

3 Summary on Findings:

It is common to sight or see heaps of rotting refuse left for days in Uyo and other heavily populated cities like Ikot Ekpene or huge dumpsites recklessly sited close to water sources in Oron and Eket unmindful of their attendant public health implications. Consequently, four findings were made in the course of the study,

The first finding was that apart from the monthly sanitation usually conducted by the state government on the last Saturday of every month in the state, the 31 Local Government Areas do not, on their own embark on sanitation exercise. Secondly, finding showed that individual families and homes in Uyo municipality collect their domestic wastes and deposit them at various dumpsites nearest to them.

It was further found that Akwa Ibom State, through the Environmental Sanitation and Protection Agency, a parastatal in the Ministry of Environment and Mineral Resources, there is provision for a regular evacuation of wastes from the various dumpsites in different streets to the central dumpsite along Uyo village road. The third finding revealed that the state government makes use of Green Brigade and consultancy under the Environmental Sanitation and Protection Agency for the day-to-day cleaning and sweeping of streets and major roads in the city.

It was further found that the Ministry of Environment has not been tasked to develop a workable and comprehensive guideline and blueprint on how to handle this type of wastes (the industrial wastes) with strict sanctions against defaulters to prevent our state from becoming a dumpsite for foreign manufacturing companies. Finally, it was found that there are no clear-cut policies that will encourage sustainable and environmental-friendly practices like the use of incineration and proposing to industries to forestall heavy metal poisoning and other catastrophic situations resulting from poor industrial waste disposals.

4 Conclusion

In conclusion, it can be inferred that environmental pollution can negatively affect the level of socio-economic development of any society if proper measures are not put in place to check or reduce its effects on the public health of the citizens of the state. This is where sustainable waste management process comes into play in Akwa Ibom State. Environmental pollution seems to be the most predominant form of pollution because it affects both land and air which comprise both human and animal environments. The need for proper attention to be paid to environmental pollution cannot be over-emphasized.

The concentration of the state government in the maintenance and sustenance of cleanliness only in Uyo metropolis is grossly inadequate. However, state government seems to handover the surrounding suburbs to Local Government Councils to handle.

But, unfortunately, however, even-though local governments are constitutionally responsible for maintenance of roads, streets, markets, abattoirs, drains, public parks, gardens and open spaces, findings show that local government authorities lack requisite tools for waste management as such contract this key function to private companies that are rarely supervised or monitored.

5 Recommendations

Therefore, based on the above findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. The Commissioner for Environment, should get all the 31 Local Government Areas actively involved in the ministry's partnerships with private sector to aid government agencies toward maintaining a clean and green environment all over the state. To achieve this, he should make efforts to keep records of

- environmental situation at the local government levels through their monthly performance reports.
2. By the same token, Akwa Ibom State House of Assembly should make laws that will curtail the production of customer bags, reduce proliferation of plastic plates/bottles as well as can drink containers in order to reduce the over-flogging of our environment with these items, especially now that the state is aspiring to be an industrial hop and will be hosting manufacturing companies. The state should prepare on how to safely dispose the envisaged industrial wastes.
 3. The Ministry of Environment should be tasked to develop a workable and comprehensive guideline and blueprint on how to handle this type of wastes (the industrial wastes) with strict sanctions against defaulters to prevent our state from becoming a dumpsite for foreign manufacturing companies.
 4. The state should make policies that will encourage sustainable and environmental-friendly practices like the use of incineration and proposing to industries to forestall heavy metal poisoning and other catastrophic situations resulting from poor industrial waste disposals.

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